

Thermophysical properties of gallic acid in aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions at different temperatures

Abhijit Sarkar and Biswajit Sinha*

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal, Darjeeling-734 013, West Bengal, India

E-mail: biswachem@gmail.com

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Density and viscosity measurements of an anti cancer agent, gallic acid in several molal concentrations $m = (0.001-0.007)$ mol.kg⁻¹ of aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions were carried out at $T = (298.15-318.15)$ K and $P = 101$ kPa. Using experimental data apparent molar volume (ϕ_V), standard partial molar volume (ϕ_V^0), the slope (S_V^*), standard isobaric partial molar expansibility (ϕ_E^0) and its temperature dependence ($\partial\phi_E^0/\partial T$)_P, the viscosity B -coefficient and solvation number (S_n), etc., were determined. Free energies of activation of viscous flow per mole of the solvents ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$) and of the solute ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$) are also calculated. Various results revealed that the solutions are characterized predominantly by solute-solvent interactions and gallic acid behaves as a long-range structure maker.

Keywords: Apparent molar volumes, viscosity B -coefficients, gallic acid, aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions, UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Introduction

Gallic acid (3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid) is a predominant polyphenol acts as a promising agent to inhibit the growth of cancer cell such as leukemia, prostate cancer, stomach cancer, lung cancer, breast cancer and show antitumor activities¹⁻¹⁰ by arresting the reactive oxygen species responsible for apoptotic cell death^{11,12}. It prevents the formation of amyloid fibrils which is a potential reason for Parkinson's disease. It is also used to prepare a number of drug intermediates including combretastatin A-4, colchicine, podophyllotoxin^{3-5,13}. It has a large numbers of therapeutically beneficial activities like antiviral, antiallergic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, nephroprotective and hepatoprotective activities¹⁴⁻¹⁹. Gallic acid acts as a strong antioxidant, an anti-radical and an antimutagen^{20,21}. It is therefore used as food additive in many processed foods to prevent the spoilage due to oxidation²². Besides this it has many industrial applications like tanning, manufacturing in paper, additive in cosmetics, color developers, corrosion inhibitor^{23,24}.

β -Cyclodextrin is a 7 membered sugar ring molecule. It can form host-guest inclusion complexes with hydrophobic molecules. β -Cyclodextrin has found a numerous number of applications in a broad range of fields²⁵. Cyclodextrins have the ability to solubilize hydrophobic drugs by providing a con-

ical cavity to encapsulate it and hence used for drug delivery. So it will be interesting to study the interaction of gallic acid in β -cyclodextrin in aqueous media. Different physico-chemical properties such as density, viscosity are used as tools to study the interactions. Although few works have been done on different properties of gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin²⁶⁻³¹, to the best of our knowledge, the properties of this ternary solution have not been reported.

Hence the purpose of the present work is to reveal the various interactions interplaying in the aqueous solutions in terms of apparent molar volumes, standard partial molar volumes and viscosity B -coefficients, solvation number etc., at $T = (298.15-318.15)$ K and at pressure $P = 101$ kPa.

Materials:

A.R. grade gallic acid (CAS: 149-91-7; Sigma-Aldrich, mass fraction purity > 0.970) and A.R. grade β -cyclodextrin (CAS: 7585-39-9, Sigma-Aldrich, mass fraction purity >0.980) were used for present study. Provenance and purity of the chemicals has been given in Table 1. The chemicals were used as such but stored *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl₂ for several hours before use. Doubly distilled de-ionized water with a specific conductance < 1.10⁻⁶ S cm⁻¹ at 298.15 K was used to prepare different aqueous solutions of β -

Table 1. Provenance and purity of the chemicals used

Chemical	Source	Purification method	Mass fraction purity	CAS No
Gallic acid	Sigma-Aldrich, Germany	None	0.990	149-91-7
β -Cyclodextrin	Sigma-Aldrich, Germany	None	0.970	7585-39-9

cyclodextrin. Various mixed solvents were prepared by mass and necessary adjustments were done to achieve exact molal concentrations ($m = 0.001, 0.003, 0.005$ and 0.007) mol.kg⁻¹ of β -cyclodextrin in the mixed solvents at 298.15 K. The physical properties of these mixed solvents are given in Table S1. Stock solutions of gallic acid in different solvent mixtures were prepared by mass and all the working solutions were prepared afresh before use by mass dilution. The mass measurements were made on a digital electronic analytical balance (Mettler, AG 285, Switzerland) with an uncertainty of $\pm 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ g. The conversion of molalities into molarities was accomplished by using experimental density data whenever needed³². Estimated standard relative uncertainty in molality of gallic acid solutions, i.e. $u_r(m)$ was evaluated to 0.01. The molecular structures of gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin are shown in Fig. 1.

Apparatus and procedure:

The densities were measured with a vibrating-tube density meter (Anton Paar, DMA 4500M). The densitometer was calibrated at the experimental temperatures with doubly distilled, degassed water and dry air at atmospheric pressure. The desired temperatures were maintained with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ K using the built-in Peltier technique. The stated repeatability and accuracy of the densities were $\pm 1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ g.cm⁻³ and $\pm 5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ g.cm⁻³, respectively. However, standard uncertainty of the density measurements for most of the solutions was found to be within ± 0.1 kg.m⁻³.

The viscosity was measured by means of a suspended Canon-type Ubbelohde viscometer thoroughly cleaned, dried and calibrated at the experimental temperatures with triply distilled, degassed water and purified methanol^{33,34}. The detail description was already described in our earlier published paper. The uncertainty in viscosity measurements was within 0.001 mPa.s.

The absorption spectra of gallic acid in aqueous solutions of β -cyclodextrin were recorded on Jasco V-530 double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer. It was coupled with thermostatic arrangement and maintained at 298.15 K. A quartz

Molecular structure of gallic acid

Molecular structure of β -cyclodextrin**Fig. 1**

cell of 1 cm path length was used and spectroscopic grade water was used to prepare all the solutions.

Results and discussion

The experimental molalities (m), densities (ρ), viscosities (η), and apparent molar volumes (ϕ_V) of gallic acid solutions in various aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions (used as solvents) at the experimental temperatures are reported in Table S2.

Standard partial molar volumes:

The apparent molar volume ϕ_V of a solute is defined as the difference between the volume of the solution and the volume of the pure solvent per mole of solute^{36–38}. The apparent molar volumes were obtained from the following relation:

$$\phi_V = \frac{M}{\rho} - \frac{1000(\rho - \rho_1)}{m\rho\rho_1} \quad (1)$$

where M is the molar mass of gallic acid, m is the molality of the solution, ρ_1 and ρ are the densities of the solvent and solution, respectively. Uncertainties in ϕ_V values were within $\pm(0.25-0.66)\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. Supplementary Table S2 shows that apparent molar volumes ϕ_V increase with increasing temperature and β -cyclodextrin content in the solutions under study. Such trends indicate that the interactions between solute and solvent as well as those between solute-solute or solute-cosolute change with temperature and solvent compositions. However, more clear information regarding solute-solute or solute-solvent interactions can be had from limiting apparent molar volumes at infinitesimal concentration or standard partial molar volumes ϕ_V^0 of the solute. As the plots of ϕ_V against square root of molar concentration \sqrt{m} were linear in the studied concentration range of gallic acid at all experimental temperatures, standard partial molar volume ϕ_V^0 were obtained from the Masson equation³⁹:

$$\phi_V = \phi_V^0 + S_V^* \sqrt{m} \quad (2)$$

Actually the ϕ_V^0 values were determined by fitting the dilute data ($m < 0.1$) to eq. (2) using a weighted least squares linear regression and the correlation coefficient (R^2) values were within the range 0.991–0.999. The weighing factors were set inverse to the variance of the ϕ_V values for each data point. The intercept ϕ_V^0 , i.e. the standard partial molar volume provides a measure of ion-solvent interactions and the slope S_V^* provides information regarding ion-ion interactions. The values of ϕ_V^0 and S_V^* along with standard deviations (σ) for gallic acid in different aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions at the experimental temperatures are reported in Table 2. Our results (Table 2) show that ϕ_V^0 values are positive and increase when both the experimental temperatures and β -cyclodextrin content in the solvents increase. This trend in ϕ_V^0 values indicates the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions and such interactions further strengthen at elevated temperatures and with higher concentrations of β -cyclodextrin in the ter-

Table 2. Partial molar volumes and the experimental slopes of eq. (2) for gallic acid in different aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions with corresponding standard deviations at $T = (298.15-318.15) \text{ K}$ and 101 kPa

$T \text{ (K)}$	$\phi_V^0 \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	$S_V^* \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3\cdot\text{kg}^{1/2}\cdot\text{mol}^{-3/2}$)	$\sigma \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)
		0.000 ^a	
298.15	139.76 (± 0.13)	-15.13 (± 0.71)	0.12
308.15	141.26 (± 0.14)	-20.50 (± 0.73)	0.12
318.15	142.88 (± 0.07)	-25.44 (± 0.38)	0.06
		0.001 ^a	
298.15	140.31 (± 0.17)	-16.67 (± 0.92)	0.15
308.15	142.14 (± 0.08)	-20.80 (± 0.44)	0.07
318.15	144.55 (± 0.08)	-27.03 (± 0.18)	0.03
		0.003 ^a	
298.15	141.62 (± 0.42)	-19.12 (± 2.24)	0.38
308.15	143.88 (± 0.15)	-26.91 (± 0.82)	0.13
318.15	146.67 (± 0.15)	-35.51 (± 1.14)	0.19
		0.005 ^a	
298.15	142.98 (± 0.28)	-23.70 (± 1.49)	0.25
308.15	145.68 (± 0.27)	-31.59 (± 1.14)	0.24
318.15	149.48 (± 0.21)	-39.40 (± 1.14)	0.19
		0.007 ^a	
298.15	143.85 (± 0.47)	-25.23 (± 2.51)	0.42
308.15	146.80 (± 0.47)	-35.18 ($\pm 0.2.53$)	0.43
318.15	150.90 (± 0.33)	-36.34 (± 1.78)	0.30

^aMolality of β -cyclodextrin in aqueous solutions in $\text{mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. Standard errors are given in parenthesis.

Standard uncertainties are: $u(T) = \pm 0.01 \text{ K}$, $u(P) = \pm 1 \text{ kPa}$, $u(m) = \pm 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$

nary solutions and such a trend in ϕ_V^0 values is at par the trends in ϕ_V values (as listed in Supplementary Table S2) for

the studied solutions. These facts may be attributed to increase in solvation of the ions at higher co-solute concentrations. Dependence of ϕ_V^0 values on the solvent composition is depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Dependence of standard partial molar volumes (ϕ_V^0) for gallic acid on the molality of β -cyclodextrin in aqueous solutions at $T = (298.15\text{--}318.15)$ K. Symbols: (\square) $T = 298.15$ K; (\circ) $T = 308.15$ K; (Δ) $T = 318.15$ K.

The parameter S_V^* is a volumetric coefficient that characterizes pair-wise interaction between the solvated species or ion-ion interaction in solution phase^{40–42}. Its sign is determined by the interactions between the solute species. In the present study, S_V^* values were found to be negative for all the studied solutions. For a species like gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin, negative S_V^* values suggest that the presence of weak pair-wise interaction between the solute-solute or the solute-cosolute and such interactions probably diminishes with increasing molality of β -cyclodextrin due to solvent induced cosphere overlap or solute-solute hydrophobic interactions⁴³.

Standard transfer volumes:

Limiting thermodynamic transfer properties provide information about the solute-cosolute interaction, because at infinite dilution the interactions between individual solute molecules are negligible. Hence $\Delta_t\phi_V^0$ is free from solute-solute interactions and provides valuable information about solute-cosolute interactions. The standard partial molar volume of transfer ($\Delta_t\phi_V^0$) were obtained from the relation⁴⁴:

$$\Delta_t\phi_V^0 = \phi_V^0[\beta\text{-cyclodextrin} + \text{water}] - \phi_V^0[\text{water}] \quad (3)$$

The $\Delta_t\phi_V^0$ values are depicted in Fig. 3 as a function of molality of β -cyclodextrin in the aqueous solutions. $\Delta_t\phi_V^0$ values are positive at all the experimental temperatures and increases monotonically with the increase in β -cyclodextrin content in ternary solutions. According to the cosphere overlap model, as developed by Friedman and Krishnan⁴⁵ the overlap of hydration cospheres of two ionic species results in an increase in volume but that of hydration cospheres of hydrophobic-hydrophobic and ion-hydrophobic groups results in volume decrease. The positive $\Delta_t\phi_V^0$ values indicate that ion-hydrophilic and hydrophilic-hydrophilic group interactions predominate over ion-hydrophobic, hydrophobic-hydrophobic and hydrophilic-hydrophobic interactions and the overall effect of the overlap of the hydration cospheres of gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin reduces the electrostriction of water by gallic acid. Such reduced electrostriction results in a concomitant increase in volume and these effect further increases with increasing molality of β -cyclodextrin in the ternary solutions increase.

The partial molar volume of a solute can also be explained by a simple model^{46,47} as given by the relation:

$$\phi_V^0 = \phi_{VW} + \phi_{Void} - \phi_S \quad (4)$$

where ϕ_{VW} is the van der Waals volume, ϕ_{Void} is the volume associated with voids or empty space, and ϕ_S the shrinkage volume due to electrostriction. Assuming the ϕ_{VW} and ϕ_{Void} to have same magnitudes in water and in aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions for the same solute, the increase in ϕ_V^0 values and the concomitant positive $\Delta_t\phi_V^0$ values can be attributed to the decrease in the shrinkage volume (ϕ_S) of water by gallic acid in presence of β -cyclodextrin. This fact suggests that β -cyclodextrin has a dehydration effect on the hydrated gallic acid. The overall positive ϕ_V^0 values indicate that ionic group interactions predominate over ionic-hydrophobic interactions. Anyway, standard partial molar volumes of a solute reflects a overall result of several solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions prevailing in solutions like: electrostatic interactions between the local charge on the solute or ions and the dipole moment of H_2O , interlocking packing interactions of the solute or ions with H_2O leading to interstitial packing or caging as well as solvation, and other polar-ionic group (H-bonding) interactions between different polar and non-polar groups of β -cyclodextrin and gallic acid; all these interactions can characterize the overall state of the solutions studied.

Apparent molar expansibilities:

Apparent molar volumes (ϕ_V) and densities (ρ) at the experimental temperatures were used to calculate the apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E) of gallic acid solutions by using the relation³⁶:

$$\phi_E = \alpha\phi_V + \frac{1000(\alpha - \alpha_1)}{m\rho_1} \quad (5)$$

where α and α_1 are the coefficients of isobaric thermal expansion of the solvent and solution, respectively and other symbols have their usual significance. α and α_1 are defined as: $\alpha = -\rho^{-1}(\partial\rho_V/\partial T)_P$ and $\alpha_1 = -\rho_V^{-1}(\partial\rho/\partial T)_P$. The uncertainty in the coefficients of isobaric thermal expansion was $\pm 2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and the uncertainty in ϕ_E values was within $\pm (0.001-0.002) \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively. The standard partial molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) were then determined from the relation⁴⁸:

$$\phi_E = \phi_E^0 + S_E \sqrt{m} \quad (6)$$

$(\partial\phi_E^0/\partial T)_P$ values were obtained from the slope of a linear fit of ϕ_E^0 values (a least squares linear regression used) against experimental temperature (T) with the correlation coefficient (R^2) values within the range 0.924–0.998. The ϕ_E^0 values are an important indicator of solute-solvent interactions and helps in interpretation of the long-range structure making or breaking properties of solutes^{49–51}. The ϕ_E^0 values along with

corresponding errors for different experimental solutions at different temperatures are given in Table 3. It reveals that ϕ_E^0 values are positive and further increase when experiment temperature and the concentration of β -cyclodextrin increase. Such a trend in values can be ascribed to the structural perturbation influenced by the gradual appearance of 'caging effect' or 'packing effect'^{52,53} for gallic acid in the studied solutions and it has hydrophobic character. According to Hepler^{54,55} if the term $(\partial\phi_E^0/\partial T)_P$ is positive, the solute is a structure maker otherwise it is a structure breaker. The $(\partial\phi_E^0/\partial T)_P$ values for different ternary solutions are given in Table 3. It shows that the $(\partial\phi_E^0/\partial T)_P$ values are positive for all the studied solutions. Thus gallic acid seems to act a net structure maker in aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions and the studied systems are characterized by the predominance of hydrophobic hydration over the electrostriction of water by the solute and cosolute molecules, i.e. some of the electrostricted water molecules in the hydration spheres of the solute, cosolute or their constituents ions get released in favor of the normal bulk structure of water upon overlap of the cospheres resulting in volume increase in coexistence of the solute and cosolute.

UV-Vis absorption spectra:

UV-Vis absorption spectra deployed to confirm the formation of the inclusion complex between gallic acid (guest) and β -cyclodextrin (host) in aqueous media. It was found β -

Table 3. Limiting partial molar expansibilities for gallic acid in different aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions at $T = (298.15-318.15) \text{ K}$ and 101 kPa

Solvent ^a	$\phi_E^0 \cdot 10^{-5} (\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1})$			$S_E \cdot 10^{-5} (\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{1/2} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1})$			$\left(\frac{\delta\phi_E^0}{\delta T}\right) \cdot 10^{-8}$ ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{kg}^{-2}$)
	298.15 K	308.15 K	318.15 K	298.15 K	308.15 K	318.15 K	
0.000	5.11 (± 0.08)	5.17 (± 0.08)	5.22 (± 0.08)	-7.20 (± 0.04)	-7.28 (± 0.04)	-7.35 (± 0.05)	5.32
0.001	10.52 (± 0.10)	10.62 (± 0.10)	10.75 (± 0.10)	-14.16 (± 0.05)	-14.29 (± 0.05)	-14.46 (± 0.01)	11.11
0.003	11.62 (± 0.02)	11.73 (± 0.02)	11.86 (± 0.02)	-14.99 (± 0.08)	-15.14 (± 0.08)	-15.31 (± 0.08)	12.32
0.005	19.47 (± 0.01)	19.65 (± 0.01)	19.89 (± 0.01)	-24.23 (± 0.07)	-24.45 (± 0.07)	-24.75 (± 0.07)	20.78
0.007	26.62 (± 0.01)	26.85 (± 0.01)	27.26 (± 0.01)	-32.18 (± 0.06)	-32.45 (± 0.06)	-32.93 (± 0.06)	31.32

^aMolality of β -cyclodextrin in aqueous solutions. Standard errors are given the parenthesis.

Standard uncertainties are: $u(T) = \pm 0.01 \text{ K}$, $u(P) = \pm 1 \text{ kPa}$, $u(m) = \pm 1 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ mol} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$.

cyclodextrin has almost no significant absorption throughout the wavelength and can be neglected. Aqueous solution of gallic acid shows a peak at 260 nm⁵⁶. The physical mixtures between gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin in aqueous solutions also show the same peak with increased intensity at all the points of wave length due to the occurrence of the inclusion between gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin.

To determine the stoichiometry and apparent formation constant for gallic acid- β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex we measured the absorption spectra of gallic acid in water and several concentrations of aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions at 298.15 K. The absorption spectrum of β -cyclodextrin ($5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹) solution did not have any considerable absorption band in the wave length range 240–300 nm and the absorption spectra of aqueous gallic acid ($1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹) solution shows a peak at 260 nm (Fig. 4). To determine the apparent formation constant for the inclusion complex of gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin, the concentration of gallic acid was held constant at $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹, in the same time concentrations of β -cyclodextrin has been manipulated as $1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹, $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹, $3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹, $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹. The absorbances of the solutions were measured at 260 nm. The absorption spectra of inclusion complex at different concentrations of β -cyclodextrin are shown in Fig. 2. It is found that the absorbance value increased with the increment of β -cyclodextrin concentrations when gallic acid concentration remains fixed. It is an indicative of the increased solubility of the guest molecules during the formation of the inclusion complex⁵⁷. The stoichiometric ratio for the inclusion complex should be 1:1, if we get a linear relationship from the reciprocal plot of $1/\text{Abs}$ vs $1/[\beta\text{-cyclodextrin}]$ based on Hildebrand-Benesi equation⁵⁸:

$$\frac{1}{A} = \frac{1}{\epsilon[G]_0 K[\beta\text{-CD}]} + \frac{1}{\beta[G]_0} \quad (7)$$

where A is the absorbance for the gallic acid solution at each β -cyclodextrin concentrations and $[G]_0$, $K[\beta\text{-CD}]$, ϵ are the initial concentration of gallic acid, apparent formation constant of gallic acid, concentrations of β -cyclodextrin and molar absorptivity, respectively. Fig. 5 shows the reciprocal plots of absorbance and concentration which determines the stoichiometric ratio for the inclusion complex formed. A good linear relationship was obtained from the graph. This graph clears

Fig. 3. Plots of standard partial molar volume of transfer ($\Delta\phi^0$) for gallic acid on the molality of β -cyclodextrin in aqueous solutions at $T = (298.15\text{--}318.15)$ K. Symbols: (\square) $T = 298.15$ K; (\circ) $T = 308.15$ K; (Δ) $T = 318.15$ K.

Fig. 4. (1) Absorption spectra of aqueous β -cyclodextrin ($1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹) solution and gallic acid with various in aqueous β -cyclodextrin concentrations, (2) 0 mol.L⁻¹, (3) $1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹, (4) $3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹, (5) $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹, (6) $7 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹.

that the ratio for the inclusion complex between gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin is 1:1. The same thing was observed by a number of researchers^{59,60}. The apparent formation constant based on the Fig. 3 was $8.70 \cdot 10^4$ L/mol.

Viscometric results:

The viscosities (η) of the different experimental aqueous solutions were analyzed by the Jones-Dole equation⁶¹:

Fig. 5. Reciprocal plot for $1/A$ vs $1/[\beta\text{-cyclodextrin}]$ of gallic acid β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex.

$$(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{c} = (\eta_r - 1)/\sqrt{c} = A + B\sqrt{c} \quad (8)$$

where $\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0$, η_0 and η are the viscosities of solvent and solution, respectively. A and B are the parameters estimated by a least-squares method and c is the concentration in molarity (calculated from molality) and reported in Table 4. Viscosity B -coefficient^{60–62} depends on solute-solvent interactions. Table 4 shows that the viscosity B -coefficients are positive and increase with the rise in the temperature. These results thus reflect strong solute-solvent interactions in the ternary solutions and suggest net structural enhancement at higher temperatures. Such interactions are also well reflected by the increase in solution viscosities induced by increasing the β -cyclodextrin concentration in the ternary solutions.

Table 4. Viscosity B -coefficients of gallic acid with the correlation coefficients R^2 , standard deviations σ for linear regression of eq. (8) along with the solvation number S_n in aqueous solutions of β -cyclodextrin at $T = (298.15\text{--}318.15)$ K and 101 kPa

Parameters	298.15 K	308.15 K	318.15 K
		0.000 ^a	
$A \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^{3/2} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1/2}$)	0.002 (± 0.000)	0.014 (± 0.001)	0.005 (± 0.000)
$B \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)	0.297 (± 0.026)	0.361 (± 0.027)	0.399 (± 0.007)
R^2	0.991	0.985	0.999
σ	0.003	0.003	0.001
S_n	2.18 (± 0.02)	2.55 (± 0.01)	2.80 (± 0.02)

Table-4 (contd.)

		0.001 ^a	
$A \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^{3/2} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1/2}$)	-0.021 (± 0.003)	-0.024 (± 0.004)	-0.013 (± 0.004)
$B \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)	0.351 (± 0.017)	0.418 (± 0.026)	0.437 (± 0.022)
R^2	0.994	0.989	0.996
σ	0.002	0.004	0.003
S_n	2.50 (± 0.02)	2.94 (± 0.01)	3.02 (± 0.01)
		0.003 ^a	
$A \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^{3/2} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1/2}$)	-0.017 (± 0.001)	-0.020 (± 0.001)	-0.019 (± 0.001)
$B \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)	0.362 (± 0.008)	0.431 (± 0.005)	0.453 (± 0.009)
R^2	0.989	0.997	0.996
σ	0.002	0.003	0.002
S_n	2.55 (± 0.01)	2.99 (± 0.03)	3.09 (± 0.02)
		0.005 ^a	
$A \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^{3/2} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1/2}$)	-0.022 (± 0.001)	-0.027 (± 0.002)	-0.029 (± 0.002)
$B \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)	0.374 (± 0.002)	0.442 (± 0.003)	0.476 (± 0.003)
R^2	0.997	0.997	0.998
σ	0.002	0.002	0.002
S_n	2.61 (± 0.01)	3.03 (± 0.01)	3.18 (± 0.02)
		0.007 ^a	
$A \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^{3/2} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1/2}$)	-0.024 (± 0.002)	-0.032 (± 0.002)	-0.027 (± 0.001)
$B \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)	0.386 (± 0.009)	0.453 (± 0.019)	0.493 (± 0.019)
R^2	0.999	0.996	0.997
σ	0.002	0.003	0.003
S_n	2.68 (± 0.03)	3.09 (± 0.02)	3.27 (± 0.03)

^aMolality of β -cyclodextrin in aqueous solutions. Standard errors are given the parenthesis.

Standard uncertainties are: $u(T) = \pm 0.01$ K, $u(P) = \pm 1$ kPa, $u(m) = \pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ mol.kg⁻¹.

Solvation number:

We have also calculated solvation or hydration numbers (S_n) for gallic acid using the relation⁶³: $S_n = B/\phi_V^0$. S_n is indicative of the formation of a primary solvation sphere around a solute. The range $S_n \approx 0\text{--}2.5$ indicates unsolvated sol-

utes⁶³ and higher S_n values indicate solvated solutes with primary solvation sphere. So an inspection of S_n values given in Table 4 indicated that most of the cases gallic acid remains solvated with primary solvation spheres in the aqueous solutions investigated here, as already discussed on the basis of ϕ_V^0 values.

Thermodynamics of viscous flow:

According to Feakings' transition state theory of relative viscosity^{64,65}, the free energy of activation of viscous flow per mole of the solute ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$) is related to the viscosity B -coefficients by the relation:

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\neq} + RT(1000B + \phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0)/\phi_{V,1}^0 \quad (9)$$

where $\phi_{V,1}^0$ and $\phi_{V,2}^0$ are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute, respectively. The free energy of activation of viscous flow for the solvent/solvent mixture per mole ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$) is given by the relation⁶⁵:

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq} = \Delta G_1^{0\neq} = RT \ln(\eta_1 \phi_{V,A}^0 / h N_A) \quad (10)$$

where N_A is the Avogadro's number and the other symbols have their usual significance. The entropy of activation for ternary solutions ($\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$) were obtained from the negative slope of the plots of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ against^{66,67},

$$\Delta S_2^{0\neq} = -d(\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq})/dT \quad (11)$$

and the activation enthalpy ($\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$) has been calculated using the relation:

$$\Delta H_2^{0\neq} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\neq} + T\Delta S_2^{0\neq} \quad (12)$$

The parameters ($\phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0$), $\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$, $\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$ and $T\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$ are reported in Table 5. It shows that $\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$ is almost invariant of the solvent compositions and temperatures, implying that $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ is dependent mainly on the viscosity B -coefficients and ($\phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0$) terms. The values $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ contain the change in the free energy of activation of solvent molecules in presence of solute as well as the contribution from the movement of solute molecules or ions. $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ values were positive and greater than $\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$ values at all the experimental temperatures for all the aqueous solvent media suggesting that solute-solvent interactions are stronger in the ground state than in the transition state and in the transition state the solvation of the solute (ions) is less favored energetically. According to Feakins *et al.*⁶⁸ the fact that $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq} > \Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$ for solutes with positive viscosity B -coefficients indicates stronger solute-solvent interactions; thereby suggesting the formation of transition state to be accompanied by the rupture

Table 5. Values of $\phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0$, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$, $T\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$, $\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$ for gallic acid in different aqueous β -cyclodextrin solutions at $T = (298.15-318.15)$ K and 101 kPa

Parameters	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K
	0.000 ^a		
$(\phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0) \times 10^6$ (m ³ .mol ⁻¹)	121.64	123.03	124.51
$\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	9.17 (±0.01)	8.95 (±0.01)	8.76 (±0.01)
$\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	66.39 (±0.27)	76.95 (±0.13)	84.20 (±0.16)
$T\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-205.56 (±1.52)	-214.46 (±1.65)	-223.37 (±1.77)
$\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-129.17 (±1.21)	-127.51 (±1.20)	-129.17 (±1.20)
	0.001 ^a		
$(\phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0) \times 10^6$ (m ³ .mol ⁻¹)	122.13	123.94	126.18
$\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	10.12 (±0.01)	10.04 (±0.01)	9.86 (±0.01)
$\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	74.69 (±0.10)	86.32 (±0.11)	90.88 (±0.13)
$T\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-241.34 (±1.42)	-249.43 (±1.42)	-257.53 (±1.44)
$\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-166.65 (±1.19)	-163.12 (±1.01)	-166.65 (±1.07)
	0.003 ^a		
$(\phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0) \times 10^6$ (m ³ .mol ⁻¹)	123.39	125.59	128.21
$\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	10.15 (±0.01)	10.07 (±0.01)	9.90 (±0.01)
$\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	76.11 (±0.09)	87.97 (±0.09)	93.19 (±0.10)
$T\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-254.56 (±1.39)	-263.10 (±1.28)	-271.64 (±1.29)
$\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-178.45 (±1.24)	175.13 (±1.24)	-178.45 (±1.21)
	0.005 ^a		
$(\phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0) \times 10^6$ (m ³ .mol ⁻¹)	124.96	127.50	131.13
$\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	10.14 (±0.01)	10.07 (±0.01)	9.91 (±0.01)
$\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	78.71 (±0.10)	90.31 (±0.12)	97.42 (±0.09)
$T\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-278.96 (±1.35)	-288.32 (±2.05)	-297.68 (±1.88)

Table-5 (contd.)

$\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-200.26 (± 1.26)	-198.00 (± 1.28)	-200.27 (± 1.28)
	0.007 ^a		
$(\phi_{V,2}^0 - \phi_{V,1}^0) \times 10^6$ (m ³ .mol ⁻¹)	125.74	128.54	132.46
$\Delta\mu_1^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	10.17 (± 0.01)	10.11 (± 0.01)	9.95 (± 0.01)
$\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	80.19 (± 0.04)	91.71 (± 0.04)	99.71 (± 0.11)
$T\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-291.13 (± 1.96)	-300.89 (± 1.96)	-310.66 (± 1.88)
$\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-210.94 (± 1.27)	-209.13 (± 1.25)	-210.94 (± 1.28)

^aMolality of β -cyclodextrin in water in mol.kg⁻¹.

Standard uncertainties are: $u(T) = \pm 0.01$ K, $u(P) = \pm 1$ kPa, $u(m) = \pm 1.10^{-2}$ mol.kg⁻¹.

and distortion of the intermolecular forces in solvent structure. The greater the value of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$, the greater is the structure-promoting tendency of a solute and the positive $\Delta\mu_2^{0\neq}$ values for gallic acid in the studied solutions suggest it to be a net structure promoter/maker. However, negative $\Delta S_2^{0\neq}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\neq}$ values suggest that the transition state is associated with bond formation between solute-solvent components and the procedure is exothermic in nature⁶⁹.

In summary, different derived parameters like ϕ_V^0 and viscosity B -coefficients for the solutions of gallic acid in the aqueous solvent systems indicated strong solute-solvent interaction between gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin and also the studied solutions are predominantly characterized by ion-solvent interactions rather than by ion-ion interactions and the gallic acid acts as a net structure promoter both in water and aqueous solution of cosolutes. S_n values indicated that the gallic acid remain solvated with primary solvation spheres in the aqueous solvent systems investigated. UV-Vis spectroscopy proves that gallic acid and β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex has performed 1:1 host guest interaction in aqueous media with an apparent formation constant of 8.70×10^4 L/mol.

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